

**ONE-STEP DWORK CONGRUENCES FOR PRIME-LEVEL
ETA-QUOTIENTS:
A UNIFORM MODULAR POLYNOMIAL METHOD**

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ABSTRACT. For a prime level N , consider eta-quotients of the shape

$$\vartheta(\tau) = \frac{\eta(\tau)^a}{\eta(N\tau)^b}$$

subject to the cusp conditions $\text{ord}_\infty(\vartheta) = 0$ and $\text{ord}_0(\vartheta) = 1$. We prove that there are exactly three such families:

$$\vartheta_2 = \frac{\eta(\tau)^{16}}{\eta(2\tau)^8}, \quad \vartheta_3 = \frac{\eta(\tau)^9}{\eta(3\tau)^3}, \quad \vartheta_5 = \frac{\eta(\tau)^5}{\eta(5\tau)},$$

of weights 4, 3, and 2, respectively. For each surviving level we show that the natural Hauptmodul

$$t_N(\tau) = \left(\frac{\eta(N\tau)}{\eta(\tau)} \right)^{24/(N-1)}$$

uniformizes $X_0(N)$ and that the associated power series

$$\Theta_N(t) = \sum_{n \geq 0} B_{N,n} t^n, \quad \Theta_N(t_N(\tau)) = \vartheta_N(\tau),$$

satisfies, for every prime $p \geq 5$ with $p \nmid N$,

$$\frac{\Theta_N(t)}{\Theta_N(t^\sigma)} - \Theta_{N,p}(t) \in p^{k_N+1} t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]], \quad t^\sigma = t_N(q^p), \quad \Theta_{N,p}(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{p-1} B_{N,n} t^n.$$

Thus the one-step exponents are p^5 for $N = 2$, p^4 for $N = 3$, and p^3 for $N = 5$. The proof is uniform: for $g_N = \vartheta_N^{-1}$ we show that

$$A_{N,p}^\sharp := -\chi_N(p) p^{k_N+1} \vartheta_N T_p(g_N)$$

is a modular function on $X_0(N)$, holomorphic away from the cusp 0, with pole order at most $p-1$ at 0. Since $X_0(N)$ is genus zero, $A_{N,p}^\sharp$ is a polynomial in the Hauptmodul t_N of degree at most $p-1$, and the Dwork congruence follows from the exact Hecke rewrite and integrality. The argument isolates the prime-level two-cusp eta-quotient class for which the modular-polynomial method closes without additional geometric input.

1. INTRODUCTION

The one-step Dwork congruence

$$\frac{F(t)}{F(t^\sigma)} - F_p(t) \in p^s t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]]$$

is a basic input in the p -adic iteration leading to higher-step Dwork towers [10]. In many geometric situations the available precision is governed by unit-root estimates in the sense of Katz [6]; in the Calabi–Yau framework of Beukers and Vlasenko one is led to a broad circle of conjectural supercongruences, notably [2, Conj. 7.5]. On the other hand, Beukers has shown that modular parametrizations often produce stronger one-step congruences than the generic expectation would suggest [3].

For the specific weight-3 eta-quotient

$$\vartheta_3(\tau) = \frac{\eta(\tau)^9}{\eta(3\tau)^3}$$

on $\Gamma_0(3)$, a companion paper proved a one-step congruence modulo p^4 by a modular-polynomial argument: one studies ϑ_3^{-1} under the Hecke operator T_p , uses a twisted Fricke commutation relation to control the pole at the non-infinite cusp, and then appeals to the genus-zero Hauptmodul of $X_0(3)$ [12, 13]. The aim of the present paper is to identify the exact prime-level class for which this mechanism survives verbatim.

The answer is rigid. If one starts with a prime level N and asks for an eta-quotient

$$\vartheta(\tau) = \frac{\eta(\tau)^a}{\eta(N\tau)^b}$$

such that $\text{ord}_\infty(\vartheta) = 0$ and $\text{ord}_0(\vartheta) = 1$, then the cusp equations force

$$a = \frac{24N}{N^2 - 1}, \quad b = \frac{24}{N^2 - 1},$$

hence integrality leaves only $N = 2, 3, 5$. These are exactly the three families

$$\vartheta_2 = \frac{\eta(\tau)^{16}}{\eta(2\tau)^8}, \quad \vartheta_3 = \frac{\eta(\tau)^9}{\eta(3\tau)^3}, \quad \vartheta_5 = \frac{\eta(\tau)^5}{\eta(5\tau)}.$$

Their weights are

$$k_2 = 4, \quad k_3 = 3, \quad k_5 = 2,$$

and the corresponding one-step exponents will be

$$k_2 + 1 = 5, \quad k_3 + 1 = 4, \quad k_5 + 1 = 3.$$

Our main theorem is as follows.

Theorem 1.1. *For $N \in \{2, 3, 5\}$, let*

$$t_N(\tau) = \left(\frac{\eta(N\tau)}{\eta(\tau)} \right)^{24/(N-1)}, \quad \vartheta_N(\tau) = \frac{\eta(\tau)^{a_N}}{\eta(N\tau)^{b_N}},$$

where

$$(a_2, b_2) = (16, 8), \quad (a_3, b_3) = (9, 3), \quad (a_5, b_5) = (5, 1).$$

Let $\Theta_N(t) \in \mathbf{Z}[[t]]$ be defined by $\Theta_N(t_N(\tau)) = \vartheta_N(\tau)$, and write

$$\Theta_{N,p}(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{p-1} B_{N,n} t^n \quad \text{if} \quad \Theta_N(t) = \sum_{n \geq 0} B_{N,n} t^n.$$

For every prime $p \geq 5$ with $p \nmid N$ one has

$$\mu_{N,p}(t) - \Theta_{N,p}(t) \in p^{k_N+1} t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]], \quad \mu_{N,p}(t) := \frac{\Theta_N(t)}{\Theta_N(t^\sigma)}, \quad t^\sigma = t_N(q^p).$$

Equivalently,

$$\Theta_N(t) - \Theta_{N,p}(t) \Theta_N(t^\sigma) \in p^{k_N+1} t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]].$$

The proof is completely uniform and hinges on a second statement.

Theorem 1.2. *Let $N \in \{2, 3, 5\}$ and let $p \geq 5$ be prime with $p \nmid N$. Put*

$$g_N := \vartheta_N^{-1}$$

and let χ_N be the quadratic nebentypus of ϑ_N :

$$\chi_2 = 1, \quad \chi_3(\cdot) = \left(\frac{\cdot}{3} \right), \quad \chi_5(\cdot) = \left(\frac{\cdot}{5} \right).$$

Define

$$A_{N,p}^\#(\tau) := -\chi_N(p) p^{k_N+1} \vartheta_N(\tau) T_p(g_N)(\tau).$$

Then there exists a unique polynomial

$$A_{N,p}(t) \in \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[t], \quad \deg A_{N,p} \leq p - 1,$$

such that

$$A_{N,p}(t_N(\tau)) = A_{N,p}^\#(\tau).$$

The exact Hecke rewrite gives

$$A_{N,p}(t) + \mu_{N,p}(t) \in p^{k_N+1} \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]],$$

while the trivial estimate $t^\sigma = t^p + O(t^{p+1})$ implies

$$\mu_{N,p}(t) - \Theta_{N,p}(t) \in t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]].$$

Because $A_{N,p}(t) + \Theta_{N,p}(t)$ has degree at most $p - 1$, these two congruences intersect exactly in $p^{k_N+1} t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]]$, which is [Theorem 1.1](#).

Two features are worth stressing.

First, the reciprocal $g_N = \vartheta_N^{-1}$ is weakly holomorphic and has the same nebentypus as ϑ_N , precisely because $\chi_N^2 = 1$. This is the point at which the quadratic character hypothesis enters. Second, the simple zero condition $\text{ord}_0(\vartheta_N) = 1$ forces the pole bound $\deg A_{N,p} \leq p - 1$ and is exactly what allows the Dwork truncation argument to close. Once one leaves this setting—for instance, by introducing zeros on \mathfrak{H} , by going to higher genus, or by allowing more complicated cusp orbits—the same modular-polynomial proof no longer closes automatically.

For related Hecke actions on weakly holomorphic forms see Guerzhoy and Moy [5, 7]. The $N = 3$ family is the symmetric-cube case treated in [12, 13]; the $N = 2$ and $N = 5$ families are obtained here by the same argument.

2. CLASSIFICATION OF THE PRIME-LEVEL TWO-CUSP ETA-QUOTIENTS

Write

$$\eta_d(\tau) := \eta(d\tau).$$

Let N be prime and consider

$$f_{a,b}(\tau) := \frac{\eta_1(\tau)^a}{\eta_N(\tau)^b}, \quad k = \frac{a-b}{2}.$$

Proposition 2.1. *For every pair of integers (a, b) one has*

$$\text{ord}_\infty(f_{a,b}) = \frac{a - Nb}{24}, \quad \text{ord}_0(f_{a,b}) = \frac{Na - b}{24}.$$

Proof. At the cusp ∞ this is immediate from

$$\eta_d(\tau) = q^{d/24} \prod_{n \geq 1} (1 - q^{dn}), \quad q = e^{2\pi i \tau}.$$

Hence

$$f_{a,b}(\tau) = q^{(a-Nb)/24} (1 + O(q)).$$

For the cusp 0 we use the Fricke matrix

$$W_N = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ N & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Since

$$\eta\left(-\frac{1}{\tau}\right) = (-i\tau)^{1/2} \eta(\tau),$$

a direct calculation gives

$$f_{a,b}|_k W_N = N^{k/2} (N\tau)^{-k} \frac{\eta(-1/(N\tau))^a}{\eta(-1/\tau)^b} = (-i)^k N^{a/2-k/2} \frac{\eta_N(\tau)^a}{\eta_1(\tau)^b}.$$

The right-hand side has order

$$\frac{Na - b}{24}$$

at ∞ , and this equals $\text{ord}_0(f_{a,b})$ by definition. □

We now impose the cusp conditions

$$\text{ord}_\infty(f_{a,b}) = 0, \quad \text{ord}_0(f_{a,b}) = 1.$$

Proposition 2.2. *Let N be prime. There exists an eta-quotient*

$$\vartheta(\tau) = \frac{\eta(\tau)^a}{\eta(N\tau)^b}$$

with

$$\text{ord}_\infty(\vartheta) = 0, \quad \text{ord}_0(\vartheta) = 1$$

if and only if $N \in \{2, 3, 5\}$. In that case (a, b) is uniquely determined by

$$a = \frac{24N}{N^2 - 1}, \quad b = \frac{24}{N^2 - 1}.$$

Equivalently,

$$\vartheta_2 = \frac{\eta_1^{16}}{\eta_2^8}, \quad \vartheta_3 = \frac{\eta_1^9}{\eta_3^3}, \quad \vartheta_5 = \frac{\eta_1^5}{\eta_5}.$$

Proof. By [Theorem 2.1](#), the cusp conditions are

$$a - Nb = 0, \quad Na - b = 24.$$

Solving gives

$$a = \frac{24N}{N^2 - 1}, \quad b = \frac{24}{N^2 - 1}.$$

Thus a and b are integral if and only if $N^2 - 1$ divides 24, which for prime N happens exactly when $N = 2, 3, 5$. \square

For later use define

$$m_N := a_N + b_N = \frac{24}{N - 1}, \quad k_N := \frac{a_N - b_N}{2} = \frac{12}{N + 1}.$$

Hence

$$m_2 = 24, \quad m_3 = 12, \quad m_5 = 6, \quad k_2 = 4, \quad k_3 = 3, \quad k_5 = 2.$$

Let

$$t_N(\tau) := \left(\frac{\eta_N(\tau)}{\eta_1(\tau)} \right)^{m_N}.$$

Then

$$\text{ord}_\infty(t_N) = 1, \quad \text{ord}_0(t_N) = -1.$$

By Newman's eta-quotient criterion, see [\[8, 11\]](#), the explicit functions t_N and ϑ_N are modular on $\Gamma_0(N)$; for the three levels under consideration their nebentypus is

$$\chi_2 = 1, \quad \chi_3(\cdot) = \left(\frac{\cdot}{3} \right), \quad \chi_5(\cdot) = \left(\frac{\cdot}{5} \right).$$

Since N is prime, $\Gamma_0(N)$ has exactly two cusps, namely ∞ and 0 . Therefore the divisor of t_N is

$$(t_N) = (\infty) - (0),$$

so t_N has degree one as a map $X_0(N) \rightarrow \mathbf{P}^1$. In particular:

Corollary 2.3. *For $N \in \{2, 3, 5\}$, the modular curve $X_0(N)$ is genus zero and*

$$\mathbf{C}(X_0(N)) = \mathbf{C}(t_N).$$

Equivalently, t_N is a Hauptmodul for $\Gamma_0(N)$.

Because η has no zeros on the upper half-plane, each ϑ_N is holomorphic and nonvanishing on \mathfrak{H} . Hence

$$g_N := \vartheta_N^{-1} \in M_{-k_N}^1(\Gamma_0(N), \chi_N).$$

The equality of characters here uses $\chi_N^2 = 1$.

Finally, because

$$t_N = q + O(q^2), \quad \vartheta_N = 1 + O(q),$$

there exists a unique power series

$$\Theta_N(t) = \sum_{n \geq 0} B_{N,n} t^n \in \mathbf{Z}[[t]]$$

such that

$$\Theta_N(t_N(\tau)) = \vartheta_N(\tau).$$

The integrality of the coefficients follows from the integral q -expansions of t_N and ϑ_N and the formal reversion $q = q(t) \in t\mathbf{Z}[[t]]$.

3. THE HECKE OPERATOR ON WEAKLY HOLOMORPHIC FORMS

For a matrix

$$\gamma = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \in GL_2^+(\mathbf{Q})$$

and an integer weight k , we use the slash operator

$$(h|_k\gamma)(\tau) := \det(\gamma)^{k/2} (c\tau + d)^{-k} h\left(\frac{a\tau + b}{c\tau + d}\right).$$

For a Laurent series $h(q) = \sum_{n \gg -\infty} a_n q^n$ define

$$U_p h = \sum_{n \gg -\infty} a_{pn} q^n, \quad V_p h = \sum_{n \gg -\infty} a_n q^{pn}.$$

Let χ be a quadratic Dirichlet character modulo a prime N , and let

$$\alpha_u = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & u \\ 0 & p \end{pmatrix} \quad (0 \leq u \leq p-1), \quad \beta = \begin{pmatrix} p & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Lemma 3.1. *Let N be prime, let $p \nmid N$ be prime, and let $h \in M_k^1(\Gamma_0(N), \chi)$. Define*

$$T_p h := p^{k/2-1} \left(\sum_{u=0}^{p-1} h|_k \alpha_u + \chi(p) h|_k \beta \right).$$

Then $T_p h$ transforms on $\Gamma_0(N)$ with character χ , and its q -expansion is

$$T_p h = U_p h + \chi(p) p^{k-1} V_p h.$$

Proof. The q -expansion identity is immediate:

$$p^{k/2-1} \sum_{u=0}^{p-1} h|_k \alpha_u = p^{-1} \sum_{u=0}^{p-1} h\left(\frac{\tau+u}{p}\right) = U_p h,$$

while

$$p^{k/2-1} \chi(p) h|_k \beta = \chi(p) p^{k-1} h(p\tau) = \chi(p) p^{k-1} V_p h.$$

To prove the transformation law, let

$$\gamma = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ Nc & d \end{pmatrix} \in \Gamma_0(N).$$

We analyze $\delta\gamma$ for $\delta \in \{\alpha_0, \dots, \alpha_{p-1}, \beta\}$.

For $\delta = \alpha_u$ one has

$$\alpha_u \gamma = \begin{pmatrix} a + Ncu & b + du \\ Npc & pd \end{pmatrix}.$$

If $a + Ncu \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, choose $u' \in \{0, \dots, p-1\}$ such that

$$u' \equiv (b + du)(a + Ncu)^{-1} \pmod{p}.$$

Then

$$\alpha_u \gamma = \gamma_u \alpha_{u'}, \quad \gamma_u = \begin{pmatrix} a + Ncu & \frac{b + du - (a + Ncu)u'}{p} \\ Npc & d - Ncu' \end{pmatrix},$$

and $\gamma_u \in \Gamma_0(N)$ with $\chi(d_{\gamma_u}) = \chi(d)$ because $d_{\gamma_u} \equiv d \pmod{N}$.

If $a + Ncu \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, then

$$\alpha_u \gamma = \gamma_u \beta, \quad \gamma_u = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{a + Ncu}{p} & b + du \\ Nc & pd \end{pmatrix},$$

again with $\gamma_u \in \Gamma_0(N)$, and now

$$\chi(d_{\gamma_u}) = \chi(pd) = \chi(p)\chi(d).$$

For $\delta = \beta$ one has

$$\beta \gamma = \begin{pmatrix} pa & pb \\ Nc & d \end{pmatrix}.$$

If $c \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, then

$$\beta \gamma = \gamma_\infty \beta, \quad \gamma_\infty = \begin{pmatrix} a & pb \\ Nc/p & d \end{pmatrix},$$

and $\chi(d_{\gamma_\infty}) = \chi(d)$.

If $c \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}$, choose $u' \in \{0, \dots, p-1\}$ such that

$$Ncu' \equiv d \pmod{p}.$$

Then

$$\beta \gamma = \gamma_\infty \alpha_{u'}, \quad \gamma_\infty = \begin{pmatrix} pa & b - au' \\ Nc & \frac{d - Ncu'}{p} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Since

$$pd_{\gamma_\infty} = d - Ncu' \equiv d \pmod{N},$$

we obtain

$$\chi(d_{\gamma_\infty}) = \chi(p)^{-1} \chi(d) = \chi(p) \chi(d)$$

because $\chi^2 = 1$.

In every case

$$\delta \gamma = \gamma_\delta \delta', \quad \gamma_\delta \in \Gamma_0(N), \quad \delta' \in \{\alpha_0, \dots, \alpha_{p-1}, \beta\},$$

and

$$\varepsilon(\delta) \chi(d_{\gamma_\delta}) = \chi(d) \varepsilon(\delta'),$$

where

$$\varepsilon(\alpha_u) = 1, \quad \varepsilon(\beta) = \chi(p).$$

Applying the same construction to γ^{-1} shows that $\delta \mapsto \delta'$ is a permutation of the $p+1$ representatives. Therefore

$$(T_p h)|_k \gamma = \chi(d) T_p h,$$

as claimed. □

4. FRICKE IDENTITIES FOR THE THREE FAMILIES

Recall

$$W_N = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ N & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Lemma 4.1. *For $N \in \{2, 3, 5\}$ one has*

$$\vartheta_N|_{k_N} W_N = \varepsilon_N t_N \vartheta_N,$$

where

$$\varepsilon_N = (-i)^{k_N} N^{6/(N-1)}.$$

Explicitly,

$$\varepsilon_2 = 64, \quad \varepsilon_3 = 27i, \quad \varepsilon_5 = -5\sqrt{5}.$$

Consequently,

$$g_N|_{-k_N} W_N = \varepsilon_N^{-1} t_N^{-1} g_N.$$

Proof. Write

$$\vartheta_N = \eta_1^{a_N} \eta_N^{-b_N}.$$

Using the eta transformation law,

$$\eta\left(-\frac{1}{N\tau}\right) = (-iN\tau)^{1/2} \eta(N\tau), \quad \eta\left(-\frac{1}{\tau}\right) = (-i\tau)^{1/2} \eta(\tau),$$

we obtain

$$\vartheta_N\left(-\frac{1}{N\tau}\right) = (-i)^{k_N} N^{a_N/2} \tau^{k_N} \frac{\eta_N(\tau)^{a_N}}{\eta_1(\tau)^{b_N}}.$$

Hence

$$\vartheta_N|_{k_N} W_N = N^{k_N/2} (N\tau)^{-k_N} \vartheta_N\left(-\frac{1}{N\tau}\right) = (-i)^{k_N} N^{a_N/2 - k_N/2} \frac{\eta_N^{a_N}}{\eta_1^{b_N}}.$$

Now

$$a_N + b_N = m_N = \frac{24}{N-1},$$

so

$$t_N \vartheta_N = \frac{\eta_N^{m_N}}{\eta_1^{m_N}} \cdot \frac{\eta_1^{a_N}}{\eta_N^{b_N}} = \frac{\eta_N^{a_N}}{\eta_1^{b_N}}.$$

Finally,

$$a_N/2 - k_N/2 = \frac{6}{N-1},$$

which yields the announced constant ε_N . □

Corollary 4.2. For each $N \in \{2, 3, 5\}$,

$$g_N|_{-k_N} W_N = c_N q^{-1} + O(1) \quad (c_N \neq 0),$$

and therefore

$$\text{ord}_0(\vartheta_N) = 1.$$

Proof. By [Theorem 4.1](#),

$$g_N|_{-k_N} W_N = \varepsilon_N^{-1} t_N^{-1} g_N.$$

Since

$$t_N = q + O(q^2), \quad g_N = 1 + O(q),$$

the right-hand side is of the form $c_N q^{-1} + O(1)$ with $c_N \neq 0$. Inverting the Fricke identity for ϑ_N gives $\text{ord}_0(\vartheta_N) = 1$. □

5. FRICKE COMMUTATION AND PRESERVATION OF WEAK HOLOMORPHY

Lemma 5.1. Let N be prime, let χ be quadratic modulo N , let $h \in M_k^1(\Gamma_0(N), \chi)$, and let $p \nmid N$ be prime. Then

$$T_p(h|_k W_N) = \chi(p) (T_p h)|_k W_N.$$

Proof. We keep the notation of [Theorem 3.1](#). First,

$$W_N \alpha_0 = \beta W_N, \quad W_N \beta = \alpha_0 W_N.$$

For $1 \leq b \leq p-1$, let $b' \in \{1, \dots, p-1\}$ be defined by

$$Nbb' \equiv -1 \pmod{p},$$

and put

$$\gamma_b = \begin{pmatrix} p & -b' \\ -Nb & d_b \end{pmatrix}, \quad d_b := \frac{1 + Nbb'}{p}.$$

Then $\gamma_b \in \Gamma_0(N)$, and a direct multiplication shows

$$W_N \alpha_b = \gamma_b \alpha_{b'} W_N.$$

Moreover

$$pd_b = 1 + Nbb' \equiv 1 \pmod{N},$$

so

$$d_b \equiv p^{-1} \pmod{N} \implies \chi(d_b) = \chi(p),$$

again because $\chi^2 = 1$. Therefore

$$h|_k W_N \alpha_b = h|_k \gamma_b \alpha_{b'} W_N = \chi(p) h|_k \alpha_{b'} W_N \quad (1 \leq b \leq p-1).$$

Since $b \mapsto b'$ permutes $\{1, \dots, p-1\}$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} T_p(h|_k W_N) &= p^{k/2-1} \left(h|_k W_N \alpha_0 + \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} h|_k W_N \alpha_b + \chi(p) h|_k W_N \beta \right) \\ &= p^{k/2-1} \left(h|_k \beta W_N + \chi(p) \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} h|_k \alpha_b W_N + \chi(p) h|_k \alpha_0 W_N \right) \\ &= \chi(p) p^{k/2-1} \left(\sum_{b=0}^{p-1} h|_k \alpha_b W_N + \chi(p) h|_k \beta W_N \right) \\ &= \chi(p) (T_p h)|_k W_N. \end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 5.2. *Under the hypotheses of Theorem 3.1, one has*

$$T_p h \in M_k^1(\Gamma_0(N), \chi).$$

Proof. By Theorem 3.1, $T_p h$ transforms on $\Gamma_0(N)$ with character χ and has bounded principal part at ∞ . Since N is prime, the only other cusp is 0.

Now $h|_k W_N$ has bounded principal part at ∞ because h is weakly holomorphic at 0. Applying the q -expansion formula of Theorem 3.1 to the Laurent series $h|_k W_N$ shows that $T_p(h|_k W_N)$ has bounded principal part at ∞ . By Theorem 5.1,

$$(T_p h)|_k W_N = \chi(p)^{-1} T_p(h|_k W_N),$$

so $(T_p h)|_k W_N$ has bounded principal part at ∞ . Equivalently, $T_p h$ is weakly holomorphic at the cusp 0. □

6. POLE ORDER AND POLYNOMIALITY

Fix $N \in \{2, 3, 5\}$ and a prime $p \geq 5$ with $p \nmid N$. Put

$$\mu_{N,p}(q) := \frac{\vartheta_N(q)}{\vartheta_N(q^p)}$$

and define

$$(1) \quad A_{N,p}^\sharp(q) := -\mu_{N,p}(q) - \chi_N(p) p^{k_N+1} \vartheta_N(q) U_p(g_N)(q).$$

Lemma 6.1. *One has*

$$A_{N,p}^\sharp(q) = -\chi_N(p) p^{k_N+1} \vartheta_N(q) T_p(g_N)(q).$$

In particular, $A_{N,p}^\sharp$ is a weakly holomorphic modular function on $\Gamma_0(N)$.

Proof. Since $g_N \in M_{-k_N}^1(\Gamma_0(N), \chi_N)$, Theorems 3.1 and 5.2 gives

$$T_p(g_N) = U_p(g_N) + \chi_N(p) p^{-k_N-1} V_p(g_N).$$

Multiplying by $-\chi_N(p) p^{k_N+1} \vartheta_N$ yields

$$-\chi_N(p) p^{k_N+1} \vartheta_N T_p(g_N) = -\chi_N(p) p^{k_N+1} \vartheta_N U_p(g_N) - \vartheta_N(q) g_N(q^p),$$

and the last term is exactly $-\mu_{N,p}(q)$. This is (1).

Because η has no zeros on \mathfrak{H} , both ϑ_N and g_N are holomorphic on \mathfrak{H} , and so is $T_p(g_N)$ by its defining sum. Weak holomorphy at the cusps follows from Theorem 5.2. Since the weights cancel, $A_{N,p}^\sharp$ is a modular function. □

Proposition 6.2. *One has*

$$\text{ord}_0(T_p g_N) = -p \quad \text{and} \quad \text{ord}_0(A_{N,p}^\sharp) = 1 - p.$$

Proof. By [Theorem 4.2](#),

$$g_N|_{-k_N} W_N = c_N q^{-1} + O(1), \quad c_N \neq 0.$$

Applying the q -expansion formula of [Theorem 3.1](#),

$$U_p(c_N q^{-1} + O(1)) = O(1), \quad V_p(c_N q^{-1} + O(1)) = c_N q^{-p} + O(1),$$

hence

$$T_p(g_N|_{-k_N} W_N) = \chi_N(p) p^{-k_N-1} c_N q^{-p} + O(1),$$

so

$$\text{ord}_\infty(T_p(g_N|_{-k_N} W_N)) = -p.$$

By [Theorem 5.1](#),

$$(T_p g_N)|_{-k_N} W_N = \chi_N(p)^{-1} T_p(g_N|_{-k_N} W_N),$$

and the scalar $\chi_N(p)^{-1}$ does not affect the order. Therefore

$$\text{ord}_0(T_p g_N) = -p.$$

Now [Theorem 4.2](#) gives $\text{ord}_0(\vartheta_N) = 1$, and [Theorem 6.1](#) yields

$$\text{ord}_0(A_{N,p}^\sharp) = \text{ord}_0(\vartheta_N) + \text{ord}_0(T_p g_N) = 1 - p.$$

□

Theorem 6.3. *There exists a unique polynomial*

$$A_{N,p}(t) \in \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[t], \quad \deg A_{N,p} \leq p - 1,$$

such that

$$A_{N,p}(t_N(\tau)) = A_{N,p}^\sharp(\tau).$$

Proof. By [Theorem 6.1](#), $A_{N,p}^\sharp$ is a modular function on $X_0(N)$, holomorphic on \mathfrak{H} . By definition (1), its q -expansion at ∞ lies in $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$, so it is holomorphic at ∞ . By [Theorem 6.2](#), its only pole is at 0, with order at most $p - 1$.

By [Theorem 2.3](#), $X_0(N)$ is genus zero and t_N is a Hauptmodul with a simple pole at 0. Therefore any modular function holomorphic away from 0 and with pole order at most $p - 1$ at 0 is a polynomial in t_N of degree at most $p - 1$. This gives a unique polynomial

$$A_{N,p}(t) \in \mathbf{C}[t], \quad \deg A_{N,p} \leq p - 1,$$

such that

$$A_{N,p}(t_N(\tau)) = A_{N,p}^\sharp(\tau).$$

Finally, $t_N = q + O(q^2)$ and $A_{N,p}^\sharp \in \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$. Thus the substitution map

$$\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[t]_{\leq p-1} \hookrightarrow \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[q]]$$

is triangular with unit diagonal, so the coefficients of $A_{N,p}(t)$ lie in $\mathbf{Z}_{(p)}$. □

7. THE ONE-STEP DWORK CONGRUENCE

Write

$$\Theta_N(t) = \sum_{n \geq 0} B_{N,n} t^n, \quad \Theta_{N,p}(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{p-1} B_{N,n} t^n.$$

Also set

$$\mu_{N,p}(t) := \frac{\Theta_N(t)}{\Theta_N(t^\sigma)}, \quad t^\sigma = t_N(q^p).$$

Proof of Theorem 1.1. From (1) and Theorem 6.3 we get

$$A_{N,p}(t) + \mu_{N,p}(t) \in p^{k_N+1} \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]].$$

On the other hand,

$$t^\sigma = t_N(q^p) = t^p + O(t^{p+1}),$$

because $t_N = q + O(q^2)$ and $q = t + O(t^2)$. Therefore the first p Taylor coefficients of $\mu_{N,p}(t)$ agree with those of $\Theta_N(t)$, and hence

$$\mu_{N,p}(t) - \Theta_{N,p}(t) \in t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]].$$

Set

$$R_{N,p}(t) := A_{N,p}(t) + \Theta_{N,p}(t).$$

Then $\deg R_{N,p} \leq p - 1$. Subtracting the last two congruences yields

$$R_{N,p}(t) \in p^{k_N+1} \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]] + t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]].$$

Because $R_{N,p}(t)$ has degree at most $p - 1$, all of its coefficients are already determined modulo t^p . Hence

$$R_{N,p}(t) \in p^{k_N+1} \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[t].$$

Finally,

$$\mu_{N,p}(t) - \Theta_{N,p}(t) = (\mu_{N,p}(t) + A_{N,p}(t)) - (A_{N,p}(t) + \Theta_{N,p}(t))$$

lies in $p^{k_N+1} \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]]$, while we already know it lies in $t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]]$. Therefore

$$\mu_{N,p}(t) - \Theta_{N,p}(t) \in p^{k_N+1} t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]],$$

which is the claimed congruence. \square

The three families are therefore:

Corollary 7.1. *For every prime $p \geq 5$ with the indicated coprimality condition, one has*

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{2,p}(t) - \Theta_{2,p}(t) &\in p^5 t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]] & (p \neq 2), \\ \mu_{3,p}(t) - \Theta_{3,p}(t) &\in p^4 t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]] & (p \neq 3), \\ \mu_{5,p}(t) - \Theta_{5,p}(t) &\in p^3 t^p \mathbf{Z}_{(p)}[[t]] & (p \neq 5). \end{aligned}$$

The $N = 3$ statement recovers the companion result of [12, 13]. The $N = 2$ and $N = 5$ statements are new consequences of the same modular-polynomial mechanism.

8. HYPERGEOMETRIC AVATARS

This section records the classical or Apéry-like realizations attached to the three surviving eta-quotients.

Remark 8.1 (The level 2 family). Using the classical theta identity

$$\theta_4(\tau) = \frac{\eta(\tau)^2}{\eta(2\tau)},$$

one finds

$$\vartheta_2(\tau) = \theta_4(\tau)^8.$$

Thus the level-2 family belongs to Ramanujan's signature-2 theory. If $\lambda(\tau)$ denotes the modular lambda function, then

$${}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; 1; \lambda(\tau)\right) = \theta_3(\tau)^2, \quad \theta_4(\tau)^2 = (1 - \lambda(\tau))^{1/2} \theta_3(\tau)^2,$$

so

$$\vartheta_2(\tau) = (1 - \lambda(\tau))^2 {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; 1; \lambda(\tau)\right)^4.$$

See Berndt–Bhargava–Garvan [1]. The level-2 family considered here should therefore be viewed as a fourth power of the classical Gauss solution, rather than as the weight-2 example attached to $\Gamma_0(2) + \langle 2 \rangle$ in [3, Appendix C, item 9.2].

Remark 8.2 (The level 3 family). The level-3 family is the symmetric-cube case of [12]. Writing

$$F(z) = {}_2F_1\left(\frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{3}; 1; z\right),$$

one has

$$\Theta_3(t) = \sum_{n \geq 0} (-1)^n \left(27^n [z^n] F(z)^3\right) t^n,$$

and

$$\vartheta_3(\tau) = \Theta_3(t_3(\tau)) = \frac{\eta(\tau)^9}{\eta(3\tau)^3}.$$

Remark 8.3 (The level 5 family). The level-5 family occurs explicitly in Beukers' Appendix C as the twisted Almkvist (η) example [3, Appendix C, item 9.6]. In his notation,

$$t(q) = \left(\frac{\eta(5\tau)}{\eta(\tau)}\right)^6 = t_5(\tau), \quad \Theta(q) = \frac{\eta(\tau)^5}{\eta(5\tau)} = \vartheta_5(\tau),$$

and the corresponding holomorphic t -series is the solution of the third-order differential operator

$$(1 + 22t + 125t^2)\theta^3 + (33t + 375t^2)\theta^2 + (21t + 375t^2)\theta + 5t + 125t^2, \quad \theta = t \frac{d}{dt}.$$

Thus the level-5 family is Apéry-like, but it is not a simple Gauss ${}_2F_1$ case.

9. COMPUTATIONAL VERIFICATION

All computations in this section were carried out in exact arithmetic with finite eta-product expansions and formal series reversion. The checks are independent of the proofs above.

For each admissible pair (N, p) with $p \leq 13$, the exact polynomial $A_{N,p}(t)$ listed in Appendices A–C has degree $p - 1$, and the identity

$$A_{N,p}(t_N(\tau)) = A_{N,p}^\sharp(\tau)$$

holds to the checked precision. In addition, the coefficients of

$$\mu_{N,p}(t) - \Theta_{N,p}(t)$$

from degree t^p through degree t^{p+4} all have p -adic valuation at least $k_N + 1$. The first nonzero coefficient and the minimum valuation among these first five coefficients are recorded in Table 1. The pair $(N, p) = (5, 5)$ is excluded, as required by the hypothesis $p \nmid N$.

TABLE 1. First nonzero coefficient of $\mu_{N,p}(t) - \Theta_{N,p}(t)$ and the minimum p -adic valuation among the coefficients of t^p, \dots, t^{p+4} .

N	p	$[t^p](\mu_{N,p} - \Theta_{N,p})$	$\min_{0 \leq j \leq 4} v_p([t^{p+j}])$
2	5	−40950000	5
2	7	−105871998960	5
2	11	−939739255564926960	5
2	13	−3029913225835118903280	5
3	5	−1023750	4
3	7	−507897936	4
3	11	−157841449993656	4
3	13	−93947556526734456	4
5	7	−1385720	3
5	11	−4581861020	3
5	13	8852899380	3

For reference, the first few t -expansions are

$$\Theta_2(t) = 1 - 16t + 496t^2 - 19456t^3 + 860656t^4 - \dots,$$

$$\Theta_3(t) = 1 - 9t + 135t^2 - 2439t^3 + 48519t^4 - \dots,$$

$$\Theta_5(t) = 1 - 5t + 35t^2 - 275t^3 + 2275t^4 - \dots.$$

These agree with the hypergeometric or Apéry-like interpretations recorded in [Theorems 8.1 to 8.3](#).

10. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

The proof above isolates the exact class for which the modular-polynomial argument closes in a purely formal way.

- The level must be prime, so that the cusp set consists of ∞ and 0 only.
- The eta-quotient must be nonvanishing on \mathfrak{H} , so that its reciprocal is weakly holomorphic.
- The Fricke transform must introduce a *simple* factor of the Hauptmodul; equivalently, the eta-quotient must have a simple zero at the non-infinite cusp.
- The nebentypus must be quadratic, so that the reciprocal carries the same character and the Fricke commutation remains scalar.

This excludes, for example, mixed CM constructions with zeros on \mathfrak{H} , higher-genus curves, and more complicated Atkin–Lehner quotients. In particular, the present theorem does not resolve the general setting of [\[2, Conj. 7.5\]](#); rather, it identifies a rigid three-family testbed in which the modular-polynomial mechanism is completely explicit.

APPENDIX A. EXACT POLYNOMIALS FOR $N = 2$

The exact polynomials $A_{2,p}(t)$ of [Theorem 6.3](#) are:

$p = 5$.

$$\begin{aligned} A_{2,5}(t) = & - 3126 \\ & - 78249984t \\ & - 49593450496t^2 \\ & - 7146825580544t^3 \\ & - 281474976710656t^4 \end{aligned}$$

$p = 7$.

$$\begin{aligned} A_{2,7}(t) = & - 16808 \\ & - 7028015104t \\ & - 20470921428992t^2 \\ & - 11516284789325824t^3 \\ & - 2243918514337349632t^4 \\ & - 175244068700240740352t^5 \\ & - 4722366482869645213696t^6 \end{aligned}$$

$p = 11$.

$$\begin{aligned}
A_{2,11}(t) = & - 161052 \\
& - 8415394037760t \\
& - 283765458929188864t^2 \\
& - 1133527918293901377536t^3 \\
& - 1350343560931072792330240t^4 \\
& - 688159606145758080912064512t^5 \\
& - 177814976959546286772433453056t^6 \\
& - 25162988208534282157737048539136t^7 \\
& - 1974048897205410235480741066571776t^8 \\
& - 80480601307289828242222693102911488t^9 \\
& - 1329227995784915872903807060280344576t^{10}
\end{aligned}$$

$p = 13$.

$$\begin{aligned}
A_{2,13}(t) = & - 371294 \\
& - 165309606133760t \\
& - 15991697908575502336t^2 \\
& - 144977771452065432731648t^3 \\
& - 352118571275174052022452224t^4 \\
& - 348412151964259628285704536064t^5 \\
& - 173063870192040828760924060909568t^6 \\
& - 48321551875634198882843087475834880t^7 \\
& - 8042744079480600715698417698311503872t^8 \\
& - 813539456388953862493415225854863081472t^9 \\
& - 48974076276699440421267867328969015558144t^{10} \\
& - 1611577289737564562962542140796854249455616t^{11} \\
& - 22300745198530623141535718272648361505980416t^{12}
\end{aligned}$$

APPENDIX B. EXACT POLYNOMIALS FOR $N = 3$

The exact polynomials $A_{3,p}(t)$ are:

$p = 5$.

$$\begin{aligned}
A_{3,5}(t) = & 624 \\
& + 2238759t \\
& + 406552365t^2 \\
& + 19758444939t^3 \\
& + 282429536481t^4
\end{aligned}$$

$p = 7.$

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_{3,7}(t) = & - 2402 \\
 & - 85463586t \\
 & - 55995812406t^2 \\
 & - 9073000431891t^3 \\
 & - 571919811374025t^4 \\
 & - 15441834907098675t^5 \\
 & - 150094635296999121t^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$p = 11.$

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_{3,11}(t) = & 14640 \\
 & + 26714715300t \\
 & + 131585427203436t^2 \\
 & + 111863014828359066t^3 \\
 & + 34290167120086502286t^4 \\
 & + 5037468737757129091638t^5 \\
 & + 404379262821033745831602t^6 \\
 & + 18738111307760623026900459t^7 \\
 & + 500374897421221254372863553t^8 \\
 & + 7152417651373927341917990787t^9 \\
 & + 42391158275216203514294433201t^{10}
 \end{aligned}$$

$p = 13.$

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_{3,13}(t) = & - 28562 \\
 & - 299145914721t \\
 & - 3491141840408331t^2 \\
 & - 5851639128621347001t^3 \\
 & - 3274893617881825617291t^4 \\
 & - 853896412429473275815788t^5 \\
 & - 122247551794069602997021188t^6 \\
 & - 10484099491496031783057154392t^7 \\
 & - 561911198531533013342012576616t^8 \\
 & - 18979085612263223801928614528727t^9 \\
 & - 392584516786777260745880745874461t^{10} \\
 & - 4542763694246994017202334345118763t^{11} \\
 & - 22528399544939174411840147874772641t^{12}
 \end{aligned}$$

APPENDIX C. EXACT POLYNOMIALS FOR $N = 5$

The exact polynomials $A_{5,p}(t)$ are:

$p = 7$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_{5,7}(t) &= 342 \\
 &+ 1017000t \\
 &+ 145687500t^2 \\
 &+ 6503906250t^3 \\
 &+ 126464843750t^4 \\
 &+ 1129150390625t^5 \\
 &+ 3814697265625t^6
 \end{aligned}$$

$p = 11$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_{5,11}(t) &= -1332 \\
 &- 82828125t \\
 &- 58732890625t^2 \\
 &- 10316582031250t^3 \\
 &- 781562011718750t^4 \\
 &- 31613098144531250t^5 \\
 &- 751609802246093750t^6 \\
 &- 10878562927246093750t^7 \\
 &- 94532966613769531250t^8 \\
 &- 454485416412353515625t^9 \\
 &- 931322574615478515625t^{10}
 \end{aligned}$$

$p = 13$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_{5,13}(t) &= 2196 \\
 &+ 528016000t \\
 &+ 734651875000t^2 \\
 &+ 222346953125000t^3 \\
 &+ 27690152343750000t^4 \\
 &+ 1823841430664062500t^5 \\
 &+ 71856491088867187500t^6 \\
 &+ 1804537296295166015625t^7 \\
 &+ 29696524143218994140625t^8 \\
 &+ 319808721542358398437500t^9 \\
 &+ 217556953430175781250000t^{10} \\
 &+ 8498318493366241455078125t^{11} \\
 &+ 14551915228366851806640625t^{12}
 \end{aligned}$$

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